

РОЛЬ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ В ОБРАЗОВАНИИ ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ

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Ruzikulova Surayo Muxiddinova

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Абстрактный.

В данной статье раскрываются роль и значение художественной литературы в воспитании детей дошкольного возраста, их художественно-эстетическом воспитании, специфические особенности детской литературы в развитии речи детей.

Ключевые слова.

образование, воспитание, художественный образ, художественная литература, фольклор, проза, иллюстрация, нравственно-эпос, нравственно-эстетический.

THE ROLE OF ART LITERATURE IN THE EDUCATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

Abstract.

This article reveals the role and importance of fiction in the education of preschool children, their artistic and aesthetic education, the specific features of children's literature in the development of children's speech.

Key words.

education, upbringing, artistic image, fiction, folklore, prose, illustration, moral epic, moral and aesthetic.

In working with children of preschool age, the artistic word has a great place. Children like to listen to folk tales, poems, stories. Children's literature, first of all, gives joy to children with its interesting content, beauty of artistic images, expressiveness of language, musicality of poetic words. At the same time, it has an educational effect on children.

Many studies have been devoted to the study of this issue, for example, teachers, psychologists, linguists K. D. Ushinsky, E. I. Tikheva, E. A. Flerina, L. S. Vygotsky emphasize the importance of introducing children to the beauty of the mother tongue, developing speech culture. they kidded. , S. L. Rubinshtein, A. V.

Zaporozhets, A. A. Leontiev, F. A. Sokhini. Children's books are considered as a means of intellectual, moral and aesthetic education. Children's poet I. Tokmakova calls children's literature the main principle of education. According to V. A. Sukhomlinsky, "reading a book is a master, skillful, intelligent, thoughtful teacher finds a way to the child's heart."

If a work of art affects a person's feelings, emotional experiences awaken a person's thinking. Excitement from a work of art activates thinking. An interesting story or picture will stimulate the game of thoughts in the child. In this regard, S. Y. Marshak said: Children are ready to hear the fairy tale "Little Red Riding Hood" 20 times. This is because the fairy tale is clear in its structure, its logic and motive are consistent, any child can put himself in the place of the hero of the fairy tale and play "Little Red Riding Hood". All types of art - literature, music, painting, sculpture, theater, cinema - are understandable to children. Art is used in decorating the kindergarten, teaching, and independent activities of children.

Preschool educational institutions can make various items and toys from clay, porcelain, wood, clay, plasticine. Good examples of children's toys can be used to decorate the group room. Carpets, textiles, pottery, goldsmithing, embroidery, pottery, art glass, metal trays, woven and embroidered flower items, etc. are part of the decorative form of visual arts. In addition, the national culture of each region, country, and republic should be used in kindergarten. The use of examples of Uzbek folk art in educational work is of great importance.

Beautiful floral fabrics with Uzbek motifs can be used for dolls' dresses, window curtains, tablecloths, etc. In the image, the desire for independence and creativity in performing the task set in all activities such as art, music, theatrical production begins to appear. When children start playing, they begin to consciously strive for expressiveness of images in pretend games. At the end of a large group, they listen carefully to music and works of art, carefully observe works of visual art, rejoice in the actions of positive characters in them, and condemn evil.

The child develops the ability to listen to music and poetry. They develop a steady interest in certain genres of music, literary and visual arts.

Music starts playing in the morning physical training, raising the mood of children. In the preschool educational organization, songs should be performed during excursions, walks and playtimes, which will bring children closer together and raise their spirits. The song performed in the process of working on the field harmonizes the rhythm of movement and gives children the joy of work. For the development of aesthetic perception in children, it is necessary to introduce them to

real works of art. Radio, mirror works performed by masters of art and peers in the world greatly help in the aesthetic development of children.

Folk art works are mainly used in playing songs, this is an extremely valuable tool for moral and aesthetic education of children. Children learn the harmony and fluency of the folk language and melody while performing folk songs and images. It educates children's sense of patriotism, forms musical taste, prepares children to perceive modern and classical tunes. In teaching to sing and dance, one is taught not only to say and act correctly, but also to say expressively and to dance lightly, gracefully and gracefully. The issue of educating children's artistic abilities is closely related to their creative growth.

Therefore, the work of teaching a child and developing his creative initiative should be carried out in a harmonious relationship with each other. The pedagogue, approaching from an educational point of view, should be able to perceive and evaluate the first, not yet fully manifested side of the child's creativity, thus he can correctly define the path of the child's development. Holidays held at MTT have a deep impact on children. The educational power and uniqueness of the holiday is that its ideological and aesthetic content is connected with various forms of art. Each holiday has its own idea, which affects children through bright images.

Therefore, the task of preschool educational institutions is, first of all, to organize the work in different areas of the child's activity, so that children have the opportunity to communicate with books on a daily basis and develop their literary interests.

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